

THE ROLE OF AI IN ENHANCING ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS: A NEW METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH FOR PHILOLOGY STUDENTS

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasining filolog talabalarining akademik yozuv ko'nikmasini shakllantirishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqildi. Mazkur tadqiqotda sun'iy intellektning o'rgatuvchi vazifalari uch bosqichda yoritib berildi. Shuningdek, sifatli natijaga erishish maqsadida promptlardan oqilona foydalanish misollar asosida ko'rib chiqildi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, sun'iy intellekt shunchaki matn yaratuvchi mexanizm emas, balki u talabalarda tanqidiy fikrlash va ilmiy sezgirlikni oshirishda yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, akademik yozuv, yozish bosqichlari, filologiya

Abstract. In this article, the opportunities of using artificial intelligence in writing academic text among philology students was analyzed. Instructional functions of AI were organized according to three stages and effective utilization of prompts was examined with examples in order to attain desirable results. The outcomes indicate that, artificial intelligence is not just text generator, it helps students to enhance critical thinking and scientific acumen.

Key words: artificial intelligence, academic writing, the process of writing, philology.

An academic essay is a piece of writing that develops an argument, provides an opinion or explores a certain topic. This type of essay follows a format, which helps to convey the ideas of writers in a logical and persuasive manner. Academic writing plays a crucial role in higher education, since it boosts critical thinking, improves interaction skills and provides learners with the capability of presenting knowledge in a structures and coherent way. It is one of the most interactive and at the same time some complex activity, therefore nowadays, most of the students especially philologists struggle with this skill. Because students have to use academic and advanced vocabulary while they are writing in order to achieve successful work. As technology continues to develop, the concept of artificial intelligence, such as ChatGPT and gemini was appeared. AI can make writing easier and convenient. However, some learners accept it as an author, it is neither legally nor ethically justified. People should perceive artificial intelligence as not only error and grammar checker, but also as a tutor that teach writing. In this research, the role of AI in developing writing skills step by step through the various stages – from planning to editing is analyzed. The followings are process of effective writing with artificial intelligence:

- Pre-writing;
- Drafting;
- Reviewing and Editing

While writing academic text, the initial process of working with AI is pre-writing. Numerous students often have writer's block and AI is beneficial in this situation, serving as an idea's generator. For instance, it can assist to make logical outline in

certain topic. Philology students often have numerous ideas, but they face challenges with putting a sequence. AI structures given notion into rational hierarchy (Introduction – Body paragraphs – Conclusion). It helps students understand that the order in which they represent their proposition make their argument stronger. Furthermore, artificial intelligence teaches learners to look at subject from different branches or angles. It leads to improvement of worldview.

The next stage is drafting, essential part of writing skill. In this step, students write their own ideas, AI transforms text to academic version and can help to enrich the learner’s vocabulary. Students usually use expressions that are common in daily communication, but academic writing requires advanced equivalent of these words. To illustrate that words like “good result”, “big issues” can spoil the quality of scientific text. Instead of these expressions, AI offer “significant outcomes” or “formidable challenges”. It demonstrates the value of language. Moreover, artificial intelligence is not just translator, but also, it is a tool for choosing synonyms and developing sentence complexity. Take “show” word as an example, AI chooses expressions that are appropriate to the particular context, such as “indicate”, “illustrate”, “reveal”, “demonstrate”. It contributes to enhance active vocabulary of student. Beside that, students are tend to make short and repeatable sentences within a text. AI illustrates the students how to turn several simple sentences into complicated and fluent statements using logical linking words. As a result, coherent and coherence of writing is enhanced.

The process of reviewing and editing is key section in writing. Analyzing grammatic and punctual errors in completed text is crucial and AI comes to help it. Artificial intelligence should explain students saying “Why do you make a mistake there?”. With the help of answering this question, student will be aware of their flaws and avoid making such kind errors in next time.

The productive use of artificial intelligence on each stage depends on students capability to give precise, accurate prompt. For philology student, AI is not just searching system, but also intellectual partner that communicate. The followings are some useful prompts:

Script	Invalid prompt	Academic prompt	Outcome
Finding academic theories	Give me theories based on subject.	"I would like to write an academic text that examines (topic name). Based on published academic papers, please suggest what theoretical frameworks exist that I can use in the introduction for my study.	Helps identify academic theories relevant to your specific topic.

Introduction structure	Write introduction part for my work.	Act as an academic advisor. I would like to write a research paper that examines (topic name). Based on published academic papers, please suggest the structure of the introduction and what I should write in every paragraph in order to craft an introduction for my work.	Provides a structured outline for writing an introduction.
Choosing a title	Give me a title for research	Suggest some interesting titles for my academic text on [specific subject]. In addition, it should be professional but engaging.	Helps suggest professional and engaging titles for your research.
Identifying literature gaps	Correct my mistake.	Can you help me identify the gaps in the current literature on [topic]? I need to point out areas where further research is required. In addition, suggest what methodological approaches I can use to fill the gaps in the literature.	Used to find "gaps" in current research to justify further study.

Students should know how to edit the text given by the artificial intelligence rather than just copying it. Using AI transforms student from passive user to active editor. When students follow instructions which are given above, they can achieve effective writing skills.

In conclusion, artificial intelligence technologies serve as an innovative tool in developing academic writing skills for philology students. The research indicates that, AI is not just text generator, but also it is virtual mentor in all stages of writing, from organizing to editing. When students possess methodological efficiency, instructional prompt competence and philological responsibility, writing academic texts become effective and easier.

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